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at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13341281>**INDICATORS OF STABLE NO METABOLITES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PANCREATITIS
COMBINED WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM****Summary**

Nitric oxide (NO) performs numerous important functions in the human body, and its pathophysiological role involves several key aspects. Considering the multifaceted action in the human body, we set ourselves the task of investigating the indicators of stable metabolites of NO in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism.

Key words *nitric oxide, chronic pancreatitis, hypothyroidism*

Introduction. One of the important directions of modern medical science is the study of comorbid conditions. In daily medical practice, there is a significant increase in the number of patients with common concomitant and combined pathologies of chronic non-infectious diseases of internal organs. Scientists from different countries are actively investigating the pathophysiological role of nitric oxide (NO) in various diseases. Excess NO is known to cause lipid peroxidation (LPO), [1,2] which can lead to the progression of inflammatory processes in the pancreas and thyroid glands. The main functions in the body are the effect on vasodilatation, antithrombotic effect, participates in the regulation of blood pressure and immune response in the body, regulation of mitochondrial function. [3,4,5]

The purpose of the study was to study the indicators of the level of stable metabolites of NO in patients with chronic pancreatitis combined with hypothyroidism.

Research materials and methods. 90 patients who, at the time of the study, were receiving inpatient treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital and in the Chernivtsi Regional Endocrinological Center during the years 2014-2021 took part in the study. 46 patients with chronic pancreatitis and 44 patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism were examined. The control group consisted of 15 practically healthy people. The intensity of nitrosative stress was assessed by the level of concentration of stable metabolites of nitric oxide (NO) (nitrites/nitrates) in the blood according to the method of L.C. Green, measuring the content of stable metabolites of nitrogen oxide (NO₂ + NO₃) in citrate plasma by a spectrophotometric method using the Griess reagent.

Research results. The results of the study show that in the comorbid course of chronic pancreatitis and

hypothyroidism, there is an increase in the level of stable metabolites of nitric oxide (nitrites/nitrates) in blood serum by 2.25 times (39.05±4.12 μmol/l, p<0.05) compared to the control group (17.28±1.45 μmol/l) and 1.65 times compared to the group of patients with chronic pancreatitis (28.57±3.04 μmol/l, p<0.05).

Conclusions Nitric oxide is a critically important molecule that is involved in many physiological processes and has a significant impact on human health. Its balance and regulation are key to the normal functioning of the body, and disruption of this balance can lead to a variety of diseases. Oxidative stress develops more intensively with a combination of chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism. Complex pharmacological effects on pathophysiological mechanisms and correction of oxidative stress can improve the treatment of such patients and prevent complications in the future.

Literature

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